

FEMININE TRADITION IN MARIA EDGEWORTH'S IRISH NOVELS

Éva Székely
University of Oradea

ABSTRACT: This paper explores the influence of the eighteenth-century feminine novel and Gothic tradition on Maria Edgeworth's Irish fiction, focusing on *Castle Rackrent*, *Ennui*, and *The Absentee*. While Edgeworth is generally regarded as a pioneer of social realism and regional Irish fiction, the study argues that her novels also preserve many conventions of sentimental and Gothic women's writing, including themes of female imprisonment, marriage, dependence, virtue, and patriarchal authority. Drawing on the traditions established by writers such as Frances Burney and Ann Radcliffe, Edgeworth reworks familiar feminine motifs within the context of Anglo-Irish society and national identity. Particular attention is devoted to the representation of women as symbolic embodiments of Ireland, especially through characters such as Ellinor, Lady Geraldine, Cecilia, and Grace Nugent. The paper demonstrates that Edgeworth both inherits and transforms the feminine literary tradition by combining Gothic conventions with realism, political allegory, and social critique. Through this synthesis, her novels move beyond the limitations of earlier feminine fiction and contribute to the development of Irish national consciousness in literature

In histories of English or Anglo-Irish literature and even in biographies or critical studies dedicated to the author herself, Maria Edgeworth is praised for her novels of Irish life which were the first works of fiction to present a careful study of Irish provincial and peasant life and manners. One of her critics: Marilyn Butler points out that "few novelists of either sex were as well qualified to make the running with social realism as Edgeworth, put by her intellectual father through a training in what we could call economics and sociology, the new 'sciences of men' of the French and Scottish Enlightenment." (Edgeworth 1992: 5) the impact that the philosophical tales of Voltaire and the writings of Marmontel had on her creation but almost completely ignores the influence of such English authors like S. Richardson, Frances Burney or Ann Radcliffe and her attitude is not a singular one, for almost all of her critics seem to forget that in the period she was writing *Castle Rackrent*, *Ennui*, *The Absentee* and *Ormond* the tradition of the gothic tale was in full bloom and that of the sentimental novel was not yet out. In fact this was the very age in which the feminine novel was born creating a lasting tradition (after all, many of the so-called 'cheap' novels or screen-scripts of soap operas of today are still written in the same vein) of a certain number of situations and themes. The present paper proposes to consider some of Edgeworth's Irish novels (namely *Castle Rackrent*, *Ennui* and *The Absentee*) in the light of the history of this genre (i.e. the feminine novel), to stress her debt to her predecessors and also to insist on the evolution of themes and characters.

The novels written by women in this period were usually epistolary novels and, by rule, love stories. The problem of marriage was one that constantly discussed and it appealed to 18th century readers. After all marriage had to be the pivot in the life of any woman in those times (and in some respect even today), the turning point from a provisional to a definite social and personal position. Hence the importance given to marriage and to the role that parents, guardians or brothers should have in the selection of a possible suitor. Besides, marriage, followed by the bearing and the bringing-up of children, always meant a complete change in the way of life of a young lady, much more, so than in that of her partner. There were several lessons that a young lady should have learned before marrying the suitable man, one of them being prudence and the other: that a woman must be worthy of her respectful admirer. One of way presenting this last requirement was through the antithetical introduction of

two characters: vice and wickedness on the one hand and virtue on the other. The unacceptable was often embodied by a French lady who had been unfortunate enough to be in some way under the pernicious influence of the French or by French chambermaids or governesses.

The principle of the plot in most novels was that the heroine, having found her necessary complement from the start would be separated from him for the most secret reasons. He would simply disappear, often without explanation, and the heroine, linked to him morally but deprived of his actual support would have to face, alone, the dangers of with which the malice and hypocrisy of man and *his* world surrounded her. Unable to rely on her partner, she soon discovered that to rely on others would lead her into disgrace, and her loneliness was therefore attended with even worse consequences than it would normally have been. Left to herself, she led a restrained life of personal grief and social misery. She became a prisoner and a victim in the sentimental novel of the sixties and the seventies; all this materialised in the Gothic novels (which under the female pen, remained to a large extent in the tradition of the sentimental genre) from the seventies onwards: it took the form of the medieval castle, the surrounding dark forests, their gangs of robbers and mischievous barons. However woman possessed a great wealth: she treasured her virginity, of course, but also her beauty, her intelligence and her obscure longings; all this was greatly insisted on. The heroine's solitude being possibly the symbol of a young lady's actual psychological and sometimes social loneliness in the world, prudence was her necessary motto. But it was as much of a rule that prudence should be defined as absolute passivity. By and large, in the 18th century novel the heroine could only wait, fear and suffer. She had no influence, except as a treasure to be conquered. She had to be rescued, which was the reverse of the attitude of Robinson or Tom Jones who fought it out until redemption came. The heroine simply waited for her social and natural complement to reveal himself; *he* would be the active agent. The implication was, no doubt, that like the heroine, a young lady could not really find a solution to her problem under the social, psychological and educational circumstances of her life. If, and when a solution presented itself, it would come by way of a miracle. In the novel it would be the result of a confession or some unlikely event of the kind, in real life it would be because some young man would have taken an interest in her, or in her family's connections and fortune. The passivity, however, was not self-sufficient, it was linked with much moral and even physical suffering to that extent that several heroines would find themselves on the verge of madness or on the threshold of death, only to be restored to sanity and immediate health at the very last moment. In most novels of the time virtue was rewarded but the sufferings of the heroine suggested that the feat was not easily achieved: merit was implied.

The quality of these first attempts was, of course, a very poor one. However, they gave a considerable satisfaction to their readers (who were ladies, of course) being the first writings to discuss their problems and to look after their world from their point of view.

The realism of these novels was limited and they seldom and only superficially referred to what the historians – most of them men – have tended to consider as the great events of the day. There were practically no references to the wars, to poverty in the cities or to any political or economical problem. An iron curtain divided the world of men's activities from that of women's; when men left the drawing room they ceased to exist. However, within these limits women did not fail in analysing and condemning several aspects of life, especially life in society. Women could only find their place in more refined surroundings, and their novels all included

one or more of the following features: the villains of the story not only tended to be horrible Lovelaces, but they would drink heavily, gamble, tolerate or even make fun of prostitution, prefer the company of their dogs and horses to that of human beings. Such people obviously could have no respect for the 'weaker sex'. We also find a number of complaints about their material situation, the main issues being concerned with women's total dependence to their parents or their husbands, and the too limited choice they had in life between celibacy, or rather the laughter-raising spinsterhood and the possibility of earning their own living as a schoolmistress or governess, who received little more respect. In her book entitled: *Subjects of Slavery, Agents of Change: Women and Power in Gothic Novels And Slave Narratives, 1790-1865*, Kari J. Winter suggests that the 'Female Gothic' developed in opposition to a 'Male Gothic' due to the differing experiences men and women have of fear, the Gothic's primary element. Where men fear 'the other' – women, Catholics, Jews – women fear the everyday. "Female Gothic novelists uncovered the terror of the familiar: the routine brutality and injustice of the patriarchal family, conventional religion and class-conscious social structures." (Winter quoted by Wixson 1996) In particular, the Female Gothic manifested a fear of complete economic powerlessness, a situation as potentially terrifying as any Bleeding Nun.

Maria Edgeworth seems very original when compared to her predecessors, though her fondness for male narrators (in *Castle Rackrent* and *Ennui*) was not really unusual with women writers who generally seemed to have experienced difficulty in using the first person, as Marilyn Butler pointed out. Her novels betray a much larger view on things, and they break away from the monotonous theme of a solitary heroine's struggles with a hostile male world though traditional themes, situations and characters persist in her writings. She was definitely influenced by Frances Burney's sentimental novels (*Cecilia* and *Evelina*) and by Ann Radcliffe's gothic novels. Many of her heroines are victimised, incarcerated by their fathers or husbands, others are epitomes of prudence and virtue and even if endowed with an autocratic character they are unable to act for themselves and thus are doomed to passive waiting for a male agent to rescue them. This is especially true for the heroines of her Irish novels, as the ones from her English ones like Lady Delacour in *Belinda* and Mrs. Beaumont in *Manoeuvring (Tales of Fashionable Life)* are dominant, even domineering. However, the former seem to us more original than the latter for, as Marilyn Buttler observed: "her Irishwomen really deserve a special attention as a group, because they have a part in the narrative itself more significantly political than the tales set in England, and because their symbolic roles (again a feature unique to her writing on Ireland) have to do directly or implicitly with national consciousness." (Edgeworth 1992: 50)

In *Castle Rackrent*, Maria Edgeworth uses the Gothic convention of imprisonment to emphasise women's marginal place in the patriarchal society of the end of the 18th century. Both Sir Kit Rackrent's wife (significantly, the reader never learns her first name) and Miss Isabella Moneygawl are locked in their rooms against their will because each refuses to accept a specific command from her husband or father, respectively. Although not physically imprisoned in a room, Sir Murtagh Rackrent's wife (another woman without a first name) is nonetheless imprisoned in her marriage because she cannot regain control of the assets she owned prior to her marriage to Sir Murtagh unless she outlives him. Her tyranny over the servants and tenants of Castle Rackrent reproduces the power relationship between husband and wife. Kari J.

Winter, in *Subjects of Slavery, Agents of Change: Women and Power in Gothic Novels and Slave Narratives, 1790-1865*, asserts that "female Gothic novelists in Britain . . . represented imprisonment and slavery as the central paradigms of woman's condition in patriarchal society"(Winter quoted by Wixson 1996). Without names of their own and described through another character's framing narrative, the literally and metaphorically imprisoned Ladies Rackrent reveal the true nature of women's social positions behind this common convention of Gothic fiction. Since the patriarchal society of the eighteenth century treated women as second-class citizens, a "realistic" novel narrated by a male character, as *Castle Rackrent* is, is likely to ignore completely the conditions of women. Placing her female characters in a Gothic subtext allows Edgeworth to express women's powerless situation through the veneer of Gothic fiction's widely acknowledged conventions.

Castle Rackrent's suggestive atmosphere is the proper background for Edgeworth's primary Gothic convention – the imprisonment of women. Winter notes that "Kate Ferguson Ellis has argued that Gothic novels "can be distinguished by the presence of houses in which people are locked in and locked out. They are concerned with violence done to familial bonds that is frequently directed against women' ". (Winter quoted by Wixson 1996) There are two such houses in *Castle Rackrent*: Castle Rackrent itself, where Sir Kit locks his wife, and the Moneygawl estate in Mount Juliet's town, where Miss Isabella is locked in her room by her father. The fact that the only two estates described in the novel are both houses in which men imprison women indicates men's ubiquitous control of women. (Winter quoted by Wixson 1996) There are two such houses in *Castle Rackrent*: Castle Rackrent itself, where Sir Kit locks his wife, and the Moneygawl estate in Mount Juliet's town, where Miss Isabella is locked in her room by her father. The fact that the only two estates described in the novel are both houses in which men imprison women indicates the absolute control that men detain over women.

Although Lady Kit Rackrent and Miss Isabella are not locked up arbitrarily, their refusals to accept men's orders provide the thin excuses needed to take away their freedom. According to Winter, "laws forbidding women to own property, to control money . . . indicate the legal denial of women's independent existence"(Winter quoted by Wixson 1996). Lady Kit Rackrent will not surrender her jewels, particularly a diamond cross, to the Rackrent estate after her marriage, which ultimately leads to her imprisonment until she turns them over to her husband. Thady's repetition of the stereotype of the wealthy Jew reminds his audience that there is a specific reason why this woman has any personal wealth at all, since "she was a Jewish by all accounts, who are famous for their great riches"(Edgeworth 1992: 76). After Sir Kit's death, Thady concludes, "Her diamond cross was, they say, at the bottom of it all; and it was a shame for her, being his wife, not to show more duty, and to have given it up when he condescended to ask so often for such a bit of a trifle in his distresses, especially when he all along made it no secret he married for money". (Edgeworth 1992: 83) Lady Kit's determination to keep her own property ironically leads to the most basic form of denial of her independent existence. She is imprisoned in a room for seven years, and escapes only because Sir Kit dies.

Mr. Moneygawl also locks Miss Isabella in her room because she disobeys him. Thady reports that Isabella "had disobliged all her relations for [Sir Condy's] sake . . . then she was locked up in her chamber and forbid to think of him anymore".(Edgeworth 1992: 86) Isabella is freed from her father's house when Sir Condy takes her to Scotland to marry her, only to be trapped at Castle Rackrent by that marriage. This pattern of imprisonment and the rescue which re-imprisons is a

variation on Edgeworth's Gothic theme. "Like enslaved protagonists, most Gothic heroines are separated from the men they love by a perverse patriarch . . . In early Gothic texts, heroines struggle bravely to be reunited with their true love, and they usually succeeded only to find that their true love is becoming a patriarch himself"(Winter quoted by Wixson 1996) Isabella's only power in her marriage comes from emotional outbursts, as when she cries and goes "into a fit of hysterics" (Edgeworth 1992: 92) over Sir Condy's nightly consumption of whiskey punch. Sir Condy agrees to stop drinking the punch, but only in immediate response to her hysterical tears, "this being the first thing of the kind he has seen"; later, Thady observes that in time she "[had] grown quite easy about the whiskey punch". Sir Condy gives Isabella relative freedom to spend and do as she pleases (especially in comparison with the previous Lady Rackrent), but still expects her money to be at his disposal. He asks his wife, "why don't [Mr. Moneygawl and others at Mount Juliet's town] show themselves your friends . . . and oblige me with the loan of the money I condescended, by your advice, my dear, to ask?"(Edgeworth 1992: 101) Sir Condy and Sir Kit condescend to ask their wives for their assets, knowing that a wife's property automatically becomes her husband's upon marriage anyway. Isabella escapes the confinement of Castle Rackrent by obtaining Sir Condy's permission to return to her family home in Mount Juliet's town; she escapes the marriage by outliving Sir Condy. Significantly, Isabella's "return to live with [her] father and [her] family" (Edgeworth 1992:103) is a mirror image of her first escape/re-imprisonment. Leaving one patriarchal home requires that she return to another.

Maria Edgeworth's merit resides not only in the fact that she took up the Gothic tradition of incarcerated women and presented it more realistically and from a male narrator's point of view. As James Newcomer observed in his bicentennial study of Edgeworth: "what is memorable about *Castle Rackrent* is an atmosphere" which consists of "whiskey, decay, rot, guttering candles, tobacco, damp, horse dung, and dust. . . . [I]t is an amalgam of improvidence, stupidity, cupidity, pride, subservience, animosity, sentimentality, brutality, and perversity"(Newcomer 1967: 154-155) and he continued: "In the heyday of the Gothic novel, Maria Edgeworth might very well have taken all these Gothic elements and marshalled them in the ingenious order of romance. Marshall them of course she did . . . but it was realism that she was after and not romance, and what in it we accept as truth is more perverse, more outlandish, and morally more revolting than the balderdash of Gothic romance"(Newcomer 1967: 155).

Heavily indebted to Frances Burney's *Cecilia*, *Ennui* is far from being as original as *Castle Rackrent*. Though, once again, things are presented from a male narrator's point of view, though the novel offers a detailed description of the life and the problems of the Irish peasantry, though gambling and epicurism are criticised, and the reader is offered yet another powerless, victimised woman (Lord Glenthorn's first wife) the novel would have passed unnoticed but for its women symbolising Mother Ireland. According to Marilyn Butler "Edgeworth's allegorical Irishwomen are a particularly strange variant of an insufficiently discussed type: the figure of a woman as a symbolical national leader, as she features in the writing of some women novelists from the late 18th century. Edgeworth began *Ennui* before the appearance of two novels which resemble it by two writers she considered rivals – Lady Morgan's *The Wild Irish Girl* (1806) which has an Irish speaking patriot heroine, and Germaine de Stael's *Corinne* (1808), whose heroine is in effect an Italian nationalist agitator."(Edgeworth 1992:51) The late 18th century trope of the nation as a woman

does not enjoy a good press in modern times. Assumed to be typically a feature of men's writing, it is thought to reflect the low esteem in which both women and defeated nations (like the Irish in our case) are held. In practice the woman novelist who imagines such a heroine generally sees to it that her authority is as short-lived and problematic as Glenthorn's reign as earl. Far from simply allowing a woman protagonist to act out clichés from the early 19th century masculine historical or colonialist yarn, the woman's version identifies the politicking and the wars as particularly male pursuits, and holds them up to scrutiny. Both the political concept and the ideal masculinity emerge undercut from this series of fictions. And here, as Marulyn Butler asserts, "*Ennui*, a naturalised representative of the genre, seems quite typical of it, since the tripartite figure of Mother Ireland, Ellinor-Geraldine-Ceciloa, lacks power in herself, and yet morlly masters the unmanly leading man, Glenthorn-O'Donoghoe" (Edgewort 1992: 51-52)

Castle Rackrent has a satirical footnote about a banshee, "a species of aristocratic fairy" which appears in the shape of "a little hideous old woman" (Edgeworth 1992:71) to warn the family in some great house that one of them is soon to die. Old Ellinor's sudden appearance before Glenthorne at his gate is the most striking manifestation of the banshee in the novel. In fact, Ellinor, the nurse, is much the most interesting and original creation, helped by a role that is maternal rather than sexual. As Glenthorn's mother in babyhood, Ellinor is Mother Ireland, Cathleen Ni Houlihan, stubborn and earthy, the most emotive and influential figure in the hero's life. Supposedly his foster-mother but in fact his natural mother, Ellinor proves to be the real mistress of Glenthorn's destiny. She appears during his 25th birthday celebrations, just when he is riding out to kill himself. She both 'kills' him in his English existence by causing a near-fatal accident and brings him to life as an Irishman by inducing him to return to Ireland. One of the means she employs is story-telling of the Irish past – always, significantly, stories of Irish rebelliousness against English rule, a fact which gives an added dimension, that of plausibility, to the subsequent association of her sons with the 1798 Rebellion. Much later in the plot, she brings the hero's reign as an earl to an end, killing him once more, by revealing the true history of his birth or rather infancy. Though the baby motif has some comic associations, its tragic potential is realised for Ellinor. The cultural difference between son and mother prevent them from understanding each other's wants. Each gives the other unwise material gifts that, as in a fairy-tale, prove burdensome and alienating. Her distress when her son gives up her gift of the earldom kills Ellinor, and she dies without being reconciled to him.

Lady Geraldine dominates the book's central chapters. Her status as an Irish patriot and spokesperson is established clumsily and schematically, by her speeches against the slavish copying of English visitors merely because they are English; and her teasing of Craiglethorpe has non of the wit of the Irish literary warfare of the 1770s on which it is remotely based. Lady Geraldine is described as having a style and an intonation that is unmistakably Irish. Simply as a talker, humorous and outspoken, she gives Irish upper-class conversation a plausible timbre of difference – even if some of her conversations sound not so much brilliant as over-assertive. The scene where Geraldine, as Irish woman, receives the proposal of Glenthorn, as English man, and to his astonishment refuses him, is one of those satisfying upsets of the favourite's form, by which novelists of the period – Frances Burney, Jane Austen and Maria Edgeworth – lightly queried society's structures of power. Her name, as Marilyn Butler observes, links her to the Fitzgeralds or Geraldines, for centuries the dominant aristocratic family in the Irish Midlands, where the Edgeworths lived. By

refusing to marry Glenthorn she anticipates his own later rejection of his estate, name and title.

Cecilia, associated more prosily to the Glenthorn estate to which she is heir, lacks the symbolic resonance of Ellinor and Geraldine. But her appearance in the plot just after Ellinor has died, has a touch of the uncanny about it: both of them are after all autochthonous creatures, who represent that part of the land of Ireland to which the hero's fate is tied. Since Cecilia enters only in the schematic closing chapters, neither her personality nor her world ever takes on the destiny of specification of the earlier chapters on the estate. The third and the last of the hero's change of identity, seems especially arbitrary. Edgeworth in fact seems to want to amuse experienced novel-readers with an elaborate play on the then celebrated ending of Frances Burney's *Cecilia*. There, the middle-class heroine, Cecilia Beverley, lost her fortune because her aristocratic fiancé Mortimer Delvile would not change his name to hers, since to do so would offend his pride of caste and gender. Burney's heroine is persuaded to give up her name and social identity, and to become Cecilia Delvile. Rearranging the counters, reversing the outcome, Edgeworth has the shadowy Cecilia Delamere emerge at the finale as the triumphant meritocrat who absorbs the dual personality representing feudalism, Glenthorn-O'Donoghoe. This is the last of the hero's transformations, and the Irish humiliations already visited on him by Geraldine now appear complete.

In *The Absentee* – which draws heavily on Frances Burney's *Evelina* – some leading women characters are more solidly drawn, that is more naturalistic, both psychologically and in their social circumstances, than the women of the first two Irish tales. *The Absentee* scores at once with its alienated Irish social climber, Lady Clonbrony, the clever, plain and equally alienated English heiress Miss Broadhurst, and a gallery of comic types from Lady Clonbrony's thankless guests to the hapless Irish hostess Mrs. Raffarty. Opposing them, the male hero, Lord Colambre, strikes the reader with its conventionality, being a somewhat livelier copy of Burney's Lord Orville from *Evelina* while his experience with Lady Dashfort (drawn on Burney's vulgar Madame Duval from the same novel) and Lady Isabel reminds one of the temptations to which Valancourt is exposed to during his stay at Paris in Ann Radcliffe's *Mysteries of Udolpho*. In its heroine, Grace Nugent – a spiritual twin-sister of Burney's Evelina as regarding prudence, obedience and love for life in the countryside – *The Absentee* repeats the essentially allegoric notion of characterisation used in *Ennui*. As Marilyn Butler observes: “Grace's name is the title of an Irish popular air. In real life the Nugents were leading Catholic gentry of the Irish Midlands, known for their principled attachment, for their religion and for their service in European Catholic armies. The name of Grace's mother, Miss St. Omer, evokes the French Catholic seminary in which Irish boys were commonly trained for the priesthood before the establishment of Maynooth in 1795. The answer to who she is, must be, a representative of the well born dispossessed Catholic gentry of Ireland.” (Edgeworth 1992: 51) As a character she seems to have no traits of her own except a desire to return to Clonbrony, and to take the absentee family of that name back to Ireland with her. But the closing stages of the plot are held up for an examination not so much of Grace's own moral character as that of her mother, long considered not to have been legally married to her father, an English officer in a foreign army. “The decoding of this mystery”, says Marilyn Butler, “requires the service of a character based on the real life Irish Catholic historian, Sylvester O'Halloran. By proving the purity of Grace and Grace's female line, the Count O'Halloran of the tale again

repeats the scholarly achievement of Dr. O'Halloran of real life: he proves the legitimacy and innate nobility of Catholic Ireland, and prepares their way of reconciliation with the Anglo-Irish Protestant gentry." (Edgeworth 1992: 51-52)

As a conclusion, when we try to define what progress has been achieved through Maria Edgeworth's pen and what is that has been preserved we may say that while on the one hand she remained remarkably conservative in dealing with the traditional themes of the feminine fiction (already mentioned at the beginning of this paper), while her heroines, if not considered as symbolical for Irish nationhood, are either paragons of virtue (e.g. Grace Nugent) or wicked, men and hypocritical (Lady Dashfort, Lady Isabel, Sir Murtagh Rackrent's wife etc.), while foolishness and breaking of the rules imposed on them by society are severely punished (Lord Glenthorn's first wife dies in misery while Isabella Moneygowl has a fatal accident when leaving Sir Condy) and parents' wishes regarding marriage have to be respected (Isabella Moneygowl has to return to her family after the failure of her marriage, initially unapproved by her father; Lady Geraldine, who fights her mother in her choice of a husband, sets off to India to live happily with Cecil Deverux, a thing which would have been impossible, had they remained in Ireland. Lord Colambre marries Grace only after the moral character of her mother proves clean and thus she is acknowledged by her grandfather and heiress to the latter's large estates, things demanded by Lady Clonbrony's from his son's future wife etc.) etc., on the other hand she gave these themes a new dimension by presenting things from men's and society's point of view. As for her success in describing Irish regional life and in giving voice in her novels to Irish national consciousness, a thing that raises her novels high above the level of the works of the pioneers of the English/Anglo-Irish feminine fiction of the 18th century, it is enough if we quote her friend and fellow writer's, Walter Scott's, praising words from the Postscript of his much acclaimed novel: *Waverley*: "It has been my object to describe these persons, not by caricatured and exaggerated use of national dialect, but by their habits, manners and feelings; so as in some distant degree to emulate the admirable Irish portraits drawn by Miss Edgeworth, so different from the 'Teagues' and 'dear joys' who so long, with the most perfect resemblance to each other, occupied the drama and the novel." (Scott 1969: 584)

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Burney, Frances (1983) *Evelina*. Bucuresti: Minerva;
- Cronin, John (1980) *The Anglo-Irish Novel* (Volume One). Belfast: Appletree Press;
- Edgeworth, Maria (1992) *Castle Rackrent and Ennui*. Harmondsworth: Penguin Books Ltd.;
- Edgeworth, Maria (1994) *Castle Rackrent and The Absentee*. London: Wordsworth Editions Ltd.;
- Newcomer, James (1967) *Maria Edgeworth the Novelist: 1767-1849. A Bicentennial Study*; Fort Worth: Texas Christian UP;
- Radcliffe, Ann (1983) *Misterele din Udolpho*. Bucuresti: Minerva;
- Scott, Sir Walter (1969) *Waverley*. London: Everyman's Library;
- Sejourne, Philippe (1999) *The Feminine Tradition in English Fiction*. Iasi: Institutul European;

Wixson, Kellie Donovan (1996) *Imprisonment in Castle Rackrent: A Gothic Convention Reflecting Eighteenth Century Women's Reality* at the Internet address <http://prometheus.cc.emory.edu/panels/1C/K.Wixson.html>